

Whole-brain imaging in rats using MRI and 3D microscopy: A cross-scale, multi-modal approach

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Introduction: Diffusion MRI (dMRI) is a powerful tool for non-invasive mapping of brain connectivity and microstructure. However, dMRI measures are indirect, noisy, and of low spatial resolution. In contrast, optical imaging of post-mortem brain tissue serves as a microstructural gold standard, which can be used to evaluate, interpret, and validate MRI contrasts [1]. Yet, mapping 2D microscopy onto 3D MRI poses many challenges. Fortunately, advances in tissue clearing [2] and light-sheet microscopy [3] enable optical imaging of intact rodent brains, thereby facilitating optimal MRI-microscopy comparisons in 3D. Whilst previous studies combined MRI and light-sheet microscopy in *mice* [4-6], our approach (Fig. 1) allows for MRI, whole-brain tissue clearing, white matter staining, and 3D microscopy of the much larger *rat* brain.

Fig. 1. A cross-scale, multi-modal approach for whole brain imaging in rats

Fig. 2. Automated pre-processing pipeline for structural and diffusion MRI of the rat brain

Methods: To optimise *ex-vivo* MRI acquisition protocols for the rat brain, we perfused 5 male Sprague-Dawley rats (Charles River, UK), with (n=3) and without (n=2) gadolinium-based contrast agent (2mM Multihance). High-resolution MRI was performed on all samples using two preclinical scanners (7T Bruker BioSpec 70/30 or 70/20 USR) with differing hardware (transmit/receive volume coil or surface cryo-coil) and software (PV6 or PV360). We optimised acquisition protocols for multi-shell (200 μm isotropic, $b=4000, 6000\text{s}/\text{mm}^2$) 90-direction dMRI, using 2D- and 3D-EPI. A T2-weighted 3D-RARE structural scan (100 μm) was also acquired. This dataset ensured that the pre-processing MRI pipeline (Fig. 2), which we developed, was generalisable to different acquisitions, data qualities, and large multi-site studies.

Rat brain hemispheres were optically cleared using a passive or active approach, with the AdipoClear+ [7] protocol and SmartBatch+ device [8-9] respectively. White matter was then stained using antibodies targeting myelin (CST #62596, Encor MCA-7G7) and neurofilament (Sigma AB1991, Encor MCA-9B12). Once the brain hemispheres were optically transparent, high resolution ($\leq 5\mu\text{m}$) volumetric imaging of sample autofluorescence (561nm) and antibody signal (640nm) was conducted using an UltraMicroscope II (LaVision Biotec) or BLAZE (Miltenyi Biotec) with InspectorPro software (LaVision BioTec). As the rat brain is larger than the field of view for 3D microscopy, multiple tiles with $\sim 30\%$ overlap were required. The resulting image stacks were stitched together using FIJI and converted to nifti format to produce a high-resolution 3D image (10 μm) of brain microstructure.

Fig. 3. Active transport of detergent and antibodies with the SmartBatch+ device accelerates clearing and labelling, whilst also preserving sample size

3D microscopy allowed us to observe specific microstructural features across the whole brain hemisphere and simplified registration to MRI. We found that even a simple affine transformation aligns MRI with 3D microscopy well (Fig. 4). Only marginal improvement was observed with a standard non-linear registration (ANTs) using the default parameters. This outcome contrasts with the complex framework required to align histology with MRI [10].

Fig. 5. Myelin staining with the SmartBatch+ provides a ground-truth measure of neuronal fibre organisation at a microscopic scale.

Results and Discussion: White matter staining, which is challenging to combine with tissue clearing, was achieved in the much larger rat brain (Fig. 3) using both passive and active approaches. The passive approach is simple but slow and results in shrinkage. In contrast, the active approach preserves sample size and is faster, but requires an electrophoretic device and expensive reagents. Additionally, we found both approaches to be compatible with gadolinium, which allows for shorter MRI acquisitions with improved SNR.

Fig. 4. Aligning autofluorescence signal, after AdipoClear+, with the corresponding T2-weighted scan is relatively straightforward.

Structure tensor analysis (which is being expanded to 3D) was used to estimate features, like fibre orientation, from microscopy (Fig. 5). These estimates will be compared with measures obtained non-invasively using dMRI.

Conclusion: By providing an end-to-end pipeline for integrating whole-brain 3D microscopy, white matter staining, and MRI in the same rat, this work paves the way for bridging microscopic information to a macroscopic resolution in larger brains, thereby improving our understanding of dMRI contrasts and the microstructural features they capture.

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